

INVESTIGATION ON THE IMPACT PROPERTIES OF GLASS FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES AT CRYOGENIC CONDITION

Hei-lam Ma¹, Kin-tak Lau^{1,*} and Jinsong Leng²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University,
Kowloon, Hong Kong SAR China

²Centre for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin, China

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ABSTRACT

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are widely used in the aerospace engineering industry due to their high specific strength to weight ratio with non-corrosive properties. Among all different types of composites, Glass fiber/epoxy (GFRP) composite is the most common and promising type that is currently used throughout the world for different engineering applications. Therefore, carrying out continuous research and development to optimize their properties is undoubtedly essential. This study aims at investigating the impact response of GFRP composites at different temperature environments, which are encountered for their service in high altitude and low earth orbit (LEO) conditions. 18 GFRP samples were produced by vacuum infusion technique and 9 of them were post-cured at 353K for 3 hours to increase their extent of cure, aiming to obtain better mechanical properties. Low velocity drop weight test was performed for the samples prepared and then stored at room temperature (288K), dry ice temperature (195K) and liquid nitrogen temperature (77K). The apparent damages and their size were carefully examined and measured, respectively. Impact parameters of samples such as load, deflection and energy absorption were obtained automatically by an impact tester and the data were analyzed on each type of damages. Experimental results showed that GFRP composites at the cryogenic condition exhibited smaller apparent damage and performed stiffer as compared with other cases. However, they also demonstrated relatively poor energy absorbability at low temperature condition.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have been widely used in many engineering applications to replace metallic structures, in particular for aerospace and aircraft structural components. Their high specific strength to weight ratio, chemical and corrosion resistances and ease of manufacturing make them attractive for many structural applications. Two recently developed aircraft, Boeing 787 and Airbus A350, consist of over 50% of FRP composites in their skins, doublers, stringers and frame structures. One of the major advantages of using these composites in aircraft is the design feasibility of using long skin panels which minimize the use of fasteners. It results in the reduction of aircraft deadweight, and thus the fuel use. In the low earth orbit (LEO) environment, where spacecrafts and satellites located, composites are always subjected to extreme temperatures in the range of -170°C to 2000°C [1]. Their reliability in this environment should be studied carefully. Therefore, it is vital to carry out continuous research and development to optimize the mechanical properties of composite materials in cryogenic condition.

Glass fibers, especially produced in a woven form, offer sufficient resistance to an object in an impact event. They have low material cost as compared with carbon fibers, which make them even more attractive for many structural applications [2]. Epoxy is one of the most popular thermoset for being the matrix of advanced composites, especially for aircraft and spacecraft components. Among all different kinds of thermosets, epoxies are famous for their promising mechanical properties such as

resistance to micro-cracking, chemical inertness, good thermal and dimension stabilities [3]. Therefore, the combination of woven glass fabric and epoxy matrix was chosen in the current study.

Shindo et al. [4] performed investigation on the tensile response of glass fiber/epoxy (GFRP) composites at cryogenic temperature and concluded that their Young's modulus and ultimate tensile stress increased when comparing with those at room temperature condition [4]. Miura et al. [5] did experiments on the fracture toughness of GFRP composites under mixed-mode II/III loading. High delamination fracture toughness was found at cryogenic temperature as compared with samples tested at room temperature environment. The out-of plane properties of GFRP composites, like impact response were also analyzed by some researchers. The influence on temperature (-50°C to 120°C) to the impact properties of GFRP laminates was examined by Salehi-Khojin et al. [6]. They discovered that the laminates became rigid with high stiffness at low temperatures and thus, their deflections in impact tests were small. Icten et al [7] also studied the effect of low temperature (-60°C to 20°C) to the impact response of composite laminates. Smaller damage area and higher perforation threshold were found at lower temperature conditions in their studies.

Although there were existing research studies about the effect of temperature on composite materials, impact response investigations focusing on cryogenic condition are still limited. In high altitude and LEO applications, impact damages on a composite structure would cause a catastrophic failure and such damages may not be observed and detected easily through naked eyes or other external non-destructive evaluation tools. As a result, they are always neglected by routine visual inspection [8]. Therefore, designing FRP composites with good impact resistance are always a major challenge to composites engineers.

This study aims at investigating the low velocity impact response of woven glass fiber/epoxy (GFRP) samples at different temperature conditions including room temperature (295K), dry ice temperature (195K) and liquid nitrogen temperature (77K). Load-deflection and energy-time curves are plotted to demonstrate the change in different parameters during an impact event. The impact properties of samples such as the damage area, deflection and energy absorption were compared.

2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

2.1 SAMPLE FABRICATION

9 GFRP samples were made for the low velocity impact test according to the standard ASTM D5628. In each sample, there are eight layers of plain woven glass fabrics. Araldite GY251 Epoxy and HY956 Hardener were mixed thoroughly in the ratio of 5:1, which is recommended by the manufacturer, to form the matrix. These materials are commonly used in the aerospace industry for the production of composite structural parts. As the mechanical properties of composites are highly sensitive to their inherent defects, good quality of samples is required. After mixing epoxy and hardener, the mixture was degassed in a vacuum jar for 15 minutes to ensure it was free of air. Vacuum infusion technique was then used to fabricate the samples. The infused samples were then kept in vacuum and allowed to cure at room temperature for 24 hours. Table 1 gives the dimensions and properties of the final samples.

Dimensions (mm)	100 x 100
Mean Thickness (mm)	1.4689 \pm 4.7%
Mean Weight (g)	23.3 \pm 4.5%
Fiber Mass Fraction	56.2%

Table 1 Dimension and Properties of GFRP Samples

2.2 SAMPLE CONDITIONING

Before performing the impact test, the samples were conditioned in three temperatures, including room temperature (295K), dry ice temperature (199K) and liquid nitrogen temperature (100K). For each temperature condition, three samples were tested. Three samples were surrounded by dry ice cubes while another three were immersed in liquid nitrogen, both in a vacuum flask for 15 minutes to allow sufficient time for the change of properties. The temperatures were recorded by a thermal couple. After that, all samples were transferred to the machine for impact test immediately.

3 EXPERIMENT SET-UP

Low velocity impact test was performed according to ASTM D5628 by a drop tower impact tester, INSTRON Dynatup 9250HV. The impactor consists of a load cell and a dart with a total weight of 17.25kg. The steel dart has a hemispheric tip with a diameter of 12.7mm. The drop height was set to 0.5m and the test energy of 8.44J was reached. During impact, the test samples were clamped by a pneumatic fixture with an inner diameter of 76mm. A velocity sensor was fixed onto the supports to monitor the impact velocity. The data obtained from the test were shown on an impulse data acquisition computer software. Load, time and impact velocity were the parameters that the machine measured while others like energy and deflection were calculated by the software automatically.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 IMPACT DAMAGE

The damage of samples made by the impactor was examined through visual inspection. Due to the small thickness of samples, the impact energy was able to transmit to the bottom layer and cause an apparent damage. Matrix cracking, delamination and minor fiber breakage were the failure mechanisms found in damaged areas. Fig. 1 shows the damages on the back and impacted side of the three groups of samples. From the figure, it can be seen that impact damages are difficult to be observed from the impacted side. It is therefore commonly neglected by routine visual inspection process [8]. The damage areas and depths of all samples were measured and the results are shown in table 2. Temperature indeed played a significant role on the size of damage under the impact test. Damage area decreases with decreasing testing temperature, which was consistent with the results proposed by Icten et al. [7]. A graph (fig. 2) was plotted to better demonstrate the trend.

Testing temperature also influenced the depth of damage. Fig 3 shows the relationship between temperature and depth of damage. Obviously, depth of damage decreases with temperature. Based on the observation of the size and depth of damages, it can be concluded that low velocity impact produced less damage to the composites at low temperature condition. The reasons behind the above phenomena will be discussed later in this paper.

Fig. 1 Back and Impacted Surface Damage

Fig. 2 Damage Size VS Temperature

Fig. 3 Depth of Damage VS Temperature

	295K	199K	100K
Damage Area (<i>mm²</i>)	108.33	95.67	90.33
Damage Depth (<i>mm²</i>)	1.843	1.275	1.023

Table 2 Damage Area and Damage Depth

4.2 LOAD-DEFLECTION CURVE

Load deflection curves against different temperatures are plotted in fig.4 according to the data generated by the testing machine. The striker rebounded in all cases and the samples did not experience perforation. Instead, they exhibited residual elastic behavior [2] so the curves are in a closed form. As there was no perforation, the maximum load that the samples could withstand was not determined in the current experiment. The slope of the load deflection curves in the elastic region and the maximum deflection were the focus. Their calculated means are list in Table 3.

From the graph, as the temperature decreases, the slope of the curves increases. The slopes of the curves are related to the bending modulus and so the stiffness of the samples. A greater slope in a load-deflection curve represents a stiffer sample. Hence, the sample becomes stiffer in the out-of-plane direction with decreasing temperature. Apart from that, the maximum deflection and the depth of damage decrease as the testing temperature decreases, which indicates that the material is less elastic at cryogenic temperature. According to Kim et al. [8], the brittleness of fibers increases at low temperature, which contributes to the greater stiffness of composites.

	295K	199K	100K
Slope at Elastic Region	0.5245	0.5876	0.6348
Maximum Deflection (mm)	8.8364	8.4325	8.1108

Table 3 Mean Slope and Mean Maximum Deflection

Fig. 4 Load-Deflection Curves of samples in different temperatures

4.3 ABSORBED ENERGY-TIME CURVE

The absorbed energy versus time curve, as shown in Fig. 5, illustrate the energy change in the samples during the impact event. Since the striker rebounded in all the cases, the maximum energy absorbed was greater than the total energy absorbed. The difference between these two values was the elastic energy given by the samples. It was a part of the total energy that was first absorbed by the samples and later returned to the surrounding areas. The majority of elastic energy was finally used to rebound the striker while a small part of it is converted into different energy forms like sound. The total absorbed energy (final energy level on the curves) is the energy absorbed by the samples to produce permanent damages and deformations. Therefore, the higher the final energy level, the greater the extent of damage.

From the absorbed energy-time curve, Fig. 5, it can be noticed that as the temperature decreases, the final energy absorbed decreases in the samples significantly. The maximum energy absorption also decreases slightly as temperature decreases as shown in fig.6. These results agreed with the findings given by Salehi-Khojin et al. [6] that the amount of energy used for producing permanent deformation decreases as the temperature decreases. As the samples absorb less energy for producing damage at low temperature, the decrease in the size and depth of damage mentioned in section 4.1 was justified. The mean of the maximum energy and final energy absorbed by the samples are list in Table 4 for reference.

An explanation for the smaller energy absorption in cryogenic temperature is the improved bonding/interface between fiber and matrix at low temperatures. In fact, both glass fiber and epoxy experience negative thermal expansion at cryogenic temperatures. Russo et al. [8] have believed that the bonding efficiency of composites plays a significant role in improving their impact properties. Besides, S.Kanagaraj and S.Pattanayak have pointed out that the negative thermal expansion of glass fiber/epoxy composites in the transverse direction mainly depends on the epoxy with the ratio of thermal expansion of epoxy to that of fiber being 15:1 [10]. Since epoxy experiences greater contraction and tightens the glass fibers, a better fiber-matrix interface is obtained. A large amount of impact energy is dissipated through the pulling out of fibers. However, the more compact interface resists fiber pull-out by increasing the friction during fiber slipping [2]. Hence, a smaller amount of energy is absorbed at cryogenic condition. Salehi-Khojin et al. [6] also mentioned the degradation of bonding with increasing temperature in their paper which further demonstrated the effect of

temperature on interfacial bonding. From section 4.1, the samples showed larger damage area at a higher temperature which might be owing to the weakening of interface at increasing temperature [11].

Though the size and depth of damage of samples at cryogenic temperature were lower, their energy absorptions were also lower. Impact resistance is always related to energy absorption and some researchers believe that the higher the energy absorption, the greater the resistance to impact [8]. For this reason, the size of damage may not be able to prove that composites behave better in cryogenic condition. It depends on how “impact resistance” is defined. Low velocity impact test with greater test energy should be performed to further understand the energy absorption at failure.

Fig. 5 Absorbed Energy VS Time

Fig. 6 Maximum energy absorbed VS Temperature

	295K	199K	100K
Max. Energy Absorbed (J)	10.3300	10.2941	10.2061
Final Energy Absorbed (J)	7.4301	6.5328	5.9737

Table 4 Mean energy values

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6 CONCLUSION

Low velocity impact tests were conducted to investigate the impact properties of glass fiber/epoxy composite samples at different temperatures in the range of 77K-298K. Although the conclusion on what temperature gives the best impact resistance was not drawn, the impact behaviors of composite samples at low temperatures were well-studied. The following conclusions were made.

- 1) The main failure mechanisms in a low velocity impact event were matrix cracking, delamination and fiber breakage.
- 2) The size and depth of damage of composite samples are smaller at decreasing temperature.
- 3) Composites are stiffer at a lower temperature, which is caused by the embrittlement of composite samples at cryogenic condition. The increase in stiffness leads to the reduction in elasticity of the sample so the deflection is smaller.
- 4) Composite sample absorbed less energy for producing damage at low temperatures since the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix was enhanced as temperature decreases. The large extent of contraction in epoxy tightened the fibers, leading to the increase in resistance during fiber pull-out.

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